

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with 4-Nitrosoresorcinol

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4-Nitrosoresorcinol reacts with cobalt nitrate to form a red complex, insoluble in chloroform.

The reaction was used to detect and determine cobalt¹ in aqueous solution by colour comparison. The present authors noted that cobalt formed mixed ligand complexes with 4-nitrosoresorcinol in presence of pyridine or some of its methyl substituted derivatives. The resulting complexes are extractable into chloroform under optimum conditions.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer. An ECL 5651 pH meter was used to measure the acidity.

Standard cobalt(II) solution was prepared from cobalt nitrate. Chloroform and pyridine bases were distilled before use. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. Acetate buffer (pH 6) was used to maintain acidity. 4-Nitrosoresorcinol was prepared using standard procedure² and recrystallised from ethanol. The reagent in the solid state is unstable but its alcoholic solution is stable.

Results and Discussion

The complexation reaction is instantaneous. On extraction with chloroform (10 ml) an equilibration period of 30 s is sufficient for quantitative extraction of cobalt. The absorbance remains constant for 24 h. The extraction behaviour of the cobalt complex as a function of pH was studied. It was found that extraction was quantitative at pH 4–7. In each case 0.1 ml of pyridine/ α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline or 2,4,6-collidine was sufficient to extract upto 200 μ g of cobalt. The mixed ligand complexes absorb maximum at 395 nm while the reagent blank absorbs insignificantly in this range. The absorbance showed a linear response over a concentration of 30 ppm of cobalt in all cases. Molar absorptivities of the complexes (on the basis of cobalt content) and the corresponding Sandell's sensitivities were evaluated (Table 1).

Interference: 177 μ g of cobalt could be determined without interference in presence of the following ions, the amounts (mg) being mentioned in parentheses: Cu^{II} (5.1), Hg^{II} (5), Ni^{II} (5.3), Pt^{IV}

TABLE 1—DETAILS OF EXTRACTIVE METHODS

Parameter	Pyri- dine	α -Pico- line	β -Pico- line	γ -Pico- line	2,4,6- Collidine
Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^3$ dm ² mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	2.12	2.09	2.99	1.89	1.65
Sandell's sensitivity (μ g/cm ²)	0.027	0.028	0.019	0.031	0.035

(3.4), La^{III} (2), Ca^{II} (6), Ba^{II} (5.7), Sr^{II} (6), Zr^{IV} (0.1), Th^{IV} (0.4), Cr^{III} (0.3), Fe^{III} (1.5 in presence of fluoride), Cd^{II} (4.9), Zn^{II} (6), Pd^{II} (5), Rh^{III} (3.2), Mn^{II} (5.2), Be^{II} (5.1), Al^{III} (0.2), Pb^{II} (0.5), U^{VI} (0.2), vanadate (20), molybdate (20), thiosulphate (7), borate (20), tartrate (20), fluoride (20), iodide (11), phthalate (20), thiocyanate (15), EDTA (0.1), phosphate (0.1), citrate (0.5), bromide (20) and ascorbate (15).

In absence of real samples, the recommended procedure was applied to the analysis of various synthetic mixtures containing 177 μ g of cobalt. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF COBALT IN VARIOUS MIXTURES WITH 500 μ g OF EACH ION ADDED

Sl. no.	Ions added	Cobalt found μ g
1.	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Fe ^{IIIa}	175.5
2.	Mn ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{IIIa}	174.5
3.	Cr ^{III} , Mn ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	176.5
4.	Hg ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	180.5
5.	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	178.5

^aPlus NH₄HF₂ (27mg)

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